

Effect of Vegetation and Organic Matter on Erodibility Status in Ukpom Abak River Catchment of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Vegetation is one of the factors that play a significant role in determining the rate of soil erodibility or susceptibility to erosion. The study is aimed at examining effect of vegetation and organic matter on erodibility status of soil in Ukpom Abak River Basin of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Data were collected with used of systematic belt transects and the simple random sampling technique. Quadrats of 5m X 120m dimensions were established with twenty-four (24) quadrats of 5m by 5m. Thereafter 20 quadrats were randomly selected. Soil samples were collected from each stream order at a depth of 0-15cm and were analysed for soil physical and chemical properties. Pearson's product correlation, stepwise multiple regression and ANOVA were the analytical tool employed for data analysis. The results revealed that soils in study area showed low K-factor. Vegetation result revealed that stems of herbaceous species enumerated (herbaceous cover) were high (66%), while the density of shrub was low (25%). In addition, density of herbs ($r = -0.401$, $p > 0.05$) and herbaceous cover ($r = -0.011$, $p > 0.05$) were inversely related to the K-factor of the River Basin, while density of shrub ($r = 0.241$, $p > 0.05$) was positively related to K-factor. There was a positive correlation between organic matter and K-factor ($r = 0.942$, $p < 0.05$). Based on the findings, the study discourage any form of illegal logging activities and deforestation, because vegetation added organic matter that bind soil aggregate, thus reduces erosion and soil loss.

Keywords: *soil erodibility, vegetation, herbaceous, herbs.*

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Introduction

Soil erosion is linked to the influence of soil properties on several processes, such as aggregate breakdown (Essien and Ogban, 2018; Ibanga *et al.*, 2025), infiltration (Idiong *et al.*, 2024), sediment detachment and transportation (Peters, 1994; Ogban and Essien, 2016; Sam *et al.*, 2025a). The term soil erodibility described soil susceptibility to erosion processes (Sheridan, 2000; Essien *et al.*, 2019). Soil erodibility is a function of complex interactions of a considerable number of physical and chemical properties of soil, which frequently vary within a standard texture class (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978). There are several definitions of soil erodibility, it can also included the relative term that can be dependent on soil characteristics.

Consequently, soil erodibility accounts for the influence of the intrinsic soil properties on soil erosion (Wang, 2001; Ogban *et al.*, 2022). Accordingly, it is possible to measure soil erodibility by investigating selected soil properties, as the present research will attempt to achieve. However, since rainfall characteristics can noticeable alter the hydraulic characteristics of soils, soil erodibility cannot be considered entirely independent from the effect of the environmental factors.

Deterioration of soil surface structure and surface seals that could occur during a rainstorm can lead to considerable variation in soil erodibility.

Soil erodibility is thus a dynamic and not a static property, so it may be change and vary over time as a result of changes and variations soil properties (Diaz-Fierros, 1996; Essien *et al.*, 2024a; Simeon and Essien, 2023). Moreover, uncertainty can be expected in soil erodibility prediction when soil erodibility is considered as a constant over time (Wang, 2001). According to Sheridan *et al.*, 2000) showed that the physical meaning of erodibility will be affected by the equation used to predict the value of the index. So, the values of erodibility have different physical meaning in each of the used predictive equations. They also suggested that the erodibility coefficient needs to be developed so that confusion is removed, and the term erodibility is clarified.

Wischmeier and Smith (1978) reported that the meaning of soil erodibility is distinctly different from that of the term soil erosion. Soil loss by erosion is also affected by other factors such as rainfall characteristics, slope percentage and length (Essien *et al.*, 2024a; Essien *et al.*, 2024b; Essien *et al.*, 2025a, plant cover and land management (Sam *et al.*, 2025b; Ibanga *et al.*, 2025), in addition to the inherent soil properties that determine soil erodibility, soil found under similar environmental conditions can have varied amounts of soil loss depending on the variation of individual soil properties and differences in soil erodibility. Thus, soil erodibility needs to be estimated independently from the effect of other factors mentioned above. Therefore, there is need to determine effect of some soil physical properties on erodibility status of soil in Ukpom Abak River Catchment Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Environment of the Study Area

The study was carried out in Ukpom Abak River Catchment Akwa Ibim State, Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is situated between latitudes $4^{\circ} 30^1$ and $5^{\circ} 30^1$ N and longitudes $7^{\circ} 30^1$ and $8^{\circ} 20^1$ E. The study area is characterised by two season (dry and wet). The dry season last from November to March, while the rainy season occurs between the months of April and October. Rainfall is heavy from 2,000 mm to 3,000. Temperatures are uniformly high throughout the year with slight variation between 26° C and 32° C. High relative humidity are common with a mean of 75%, while solar radiation ranges from 6 – 15 KJ per day (Petter *et al.*, 1989).

The soil are derived from sandy parent materials and are highly weathered and dominated by low activity of clays. Sands are clays from river deposition cover a greater part of the state and constitute the Benin formation, also known as the coastal plain sands. They originated from the tertially sandstones with the low shale and Ameki formation (Petter *et al.*, 1989). The natural vegetation is mainly savannah with some redict of rainforest distribution in patches. The nature vegetation has been almost completely replaced by secondary forest of predominantly wild, oil palm, wood shrubs such as chromolaena odorata and various grass under growth.

Figure 1. Map Showing Soil Sample Locations at Ukpom Abak River Catchment
 Source: Akwa Ibom State Geographical Information Agency

Stream Ordering

Stream ordering was done to know the extent of the Ukpom Abak River Catchment and to enable the researcher to partition it into sites for the study. The method adopted was first proposed by Graveluis in 1914 and later modified by Strahler (1957). This method of stream ordering has it that each finger-tip tributary is designated a first order stream, two stream of the same order combine to give the next order stream such that two second order streams combine to give a third order stream and so on. Once this initial ordering has been completed the highest order stream was projected back to head waters along the stream which involved least deviation from the mainstream direction. To order the drainage network in two stages was complicated, as it entailed an additional subjective decision in projecting the order of streams headward. And in addition, all smallest un-branched tributaries are not of the same order, as affirmed by Gregory and Walling (1973).

Field Methods and Sampling Techniques

The studys was conducted in Ukpom Abak Catchment Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Soil samples were taken with a soil auger at 0 - 20 cm depth from the two sites into which the River Catchment was divided during stream ordering. A total of 20 composite soil samples were collected and taken to the

laboratory for analyses. The soil samples were air-dried, crushed and sieved with a 2 mm mesh sieve for the organic matter determination, by standard methods, as described by Udo *et al.* (2009).

Laboratory Analysis

Soil physical properties

The proportions of sand, silt and clay particles (particle size distribution) in the soil samples were determined by the Bouyoucous Hydrometer method using sodium hexametaphosphate (calgon) as the dispersing agent. The proportions of fine and very fine sand in each soil sample were determined by the sieving method, while the texture of each soil sample was determined using the soil textural triangle. Bulk density, particle density, porosity moisture content water aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity were determined by the routine methods.

Soil chemical properties

The pH of the soils was measured with a glass electrode pH meter at the soil/water ratio of 1: 2.5. The organic matter contents of the soils were determined by the Walkley-Black wet oxidation method. The Walkley-Black procedure measures active or decomposable organic matter in the soil. The reagents used were potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$), concentrated sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) and ferrous complex as indicator.

Determination of Soil Erodibility Status

The nomograph model/equation was used (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978) to estimate the erodibility status (K-factor) of the soils. The following soil parameters were employed:

- (i.) Percentage silt + very fine sand
- (ii.) Percentage sand
- (iii.) Organic matter content
- (iv.) Soil structure Permeability class.

As reported by Cassol *et al.* (2018), the nomograph model is mathematically expressed as follows:

$$K = 2.1 M^{1.14} (10^{-4}) (12 - Y) + 3.25 (S - 2) + 2.5 (P - 3)/100 \quad (1)$$

Where:

K = USLE soil erodibility (K-factor)

M = Product of (% silt + % fine sand) and (100 - % clay)

Y = Organic matter content in percentage

S = Soil structure class/grade (1 for very fine granular soil; 2 for fine granular soil; 3 for medium or coarse granular soil; 4 is for blocky, platy or massive soil; Ibaje, 2016);

P = Permeability class (1 for very slow infiltration; 2 for slow infiltration; 3 for slow to moderate infiltration; 4 for moderate infiltration; 5 for moderate to rapid infiltration; 6 for rapid infiltration (Essien, 2013).

Expressing in the SI unit ($t\ ha\ h\ ha^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$), the K-value was multiplied by 0.1312 (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978; Cassol *et al.*, 2018) after which it was rated, according to Ibaje (2016) thus: Very high > 0.45; high = 0.35 - 0.45; moderate = 0.25 - 0.35; low to very low = < 0.2. In addition to this classification, the study employed the standard erodibility indices in Table 1 (Emeka-Chris, 2014; Okorafor *et al.*, 2018) to determine the status of K-factor.

Table 1. Standard Erodibility Indices

Group	K-value	Nature of soil
I	0.0 – 0.1	Permeable out wash well drained soil, slowly permeable substrata
II	0.11 – 0.17	Well grained soils in sandy gravel free material
III	0.18 – 0.28	Graded loams and silt loams
IV	0.29 – 0.48	Poorly graded moderately fine textured soil
V	0.49 – 0.64	Poorly graded silt, very fine sandy soil, well and moderately graded

Source: Emeka-Chris (2014) and Okorafor (2018)

Data Analysis

Data obtained were analyzed using tables, averages, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and stepwise multiple regression. Statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version (22.0) for Windows and excel spreadsheet.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation

The correlation coefficients determined were used to assess the relationships between soil erodibility status and vegetation components/selected soil properties. The correlation analysis was based on the following formula:

$$r = \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2 n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}} \tag{2}$$

Where

r = Correlation coefficient

x and y = The two variables of interest

∑ = Summation

While the negative values indicated inverse relationships, the positive values indicated direct relationships.

Stepwise Multiple Linear Regression

The stepwise multiple linear regression is a method of regressing multiple variables while simultaneously eliminating insignificant variables. Multiple regression analysis is an extension of simple linear regression. It was used to predict the value of a variable based on the value of two or more other variables. This technique is appropriate because it shows us the relative effect the combination of sand, silt, clay and organic matter has on K-factor. The test identified the soil property that contributed most to the changes in K-factor in the study area. The multiple regression analysis was based on the relation mathematically defined as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_{14}X_{14} + e \tag{3}$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable (K-factor),

a = Y-intercept,

X1- X14 = Independent variables

X1 = Sand (%), X2 = Silt (%),

X₃ = Clay (%), X₄ = Organic matter (%)

X₅ = Hydraulic conductivity (cm/sec),

X₆ = Water aggregate stability (%),

X₇ = Soil moisture (%),

X₈ = Bulk density (g/cm³),

X₉ = Particle density,

X₁₀ = Porosity (%),

X₁₁ = Density of herbs,

X₁₂ = Herbaceous cover (%),

X₁₃ = Shrub density

X₁₄ = pH,

b₁– b₁₄ = Regression coefficients,

e = Error term.

Results and Discussion

The density of herbs around and within the river catchment plays a significant roles in soil erosion control. They help to loosen the soil for easy penetration of rainwater as well as afford the soil protective cover to assuage the direct impact on rainwater. Herbaceous plants help the river catchment environment by enhancing water quality and biodiversity, but they also help more directly by increasing land value. Naylor *et al.* (2002) stated that the effects of vegetation components on soils are divided into two major effects: bioprotection and bioconstruction. Plant cover protects soils against erosion by reducing water runoff (Zuazo & Pleguezuelo, 2009) and by increasing water infiltration into the soil matrix (Wainwright *et al.*, 2002). Also, vegetation *can* act as a physical barrier, altering sediment flow at the soil surface (Martinez *et al.*, 2006).

Table 2. General Herbaceous Species Composition in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

S/N	Scientific names	Common names	Species family	Freq
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	72
2	<i>Axomopus compresus</i>	Carpet grass	Poaceae	6
3	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Sensitive plant	Fabaceae	27
4	<i>Amaranthus spinose</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	31
5	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	48
6	<i>Urena lobata</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	24
7	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	51
8	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Red spidering	Nyctaginaceae	6
9	<i>Laripatea aesthes</i>	Stringing herb	Peperaceae	4
10	<i>Peperomia pellucid</i>	Silver plant	Urticaceae	6
11	<i>Spermacole ocymoides</i>	Ezecma plant	Rubiaceae	11

12	<i>Saccharum octocinatum</i>	Sugar cane	Andropogonem	16
13	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Bull grass	Poaceae	14
14	<i>Laripater ovalifolia</i>	Striging nettle	Urticaceae	9
15	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	26
16	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	18
17	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	22
18	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	46
19	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	Euphorbiaceae	35
20	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	43
21	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	11
22	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	18
23	<i>Spigelia enthelmia</i>	Warm weed	Potaliaceae	11
24	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i>	Blue cento	Fabaceae	12
25	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	16
26	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	22
27	<i>Commelina beghalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	21
28	<i>Drymorina cordata</i>		Caryophylliaceae	4
29	<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i>	Consumption weed	Corpparidaceae	6
30	<i>Croton lobutus</i>		Euphorbiaceae	5
31	<i>Echinochloa pyramidalis</i>		Poaceae	2
32	<i>Paspalum arbuticlane</i>	Ditch mullet	Poaceae	5
33	<i>Gloriosa superb</i>	Lily	Liliaceae	2
34	<i>Spermacole venticillata</i>		Rubiaceae	2
35	<i>Kyllingo bulbosa</i>	Sedge	Cyparaceae	6
36	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Beni seed	Pedaliaceae	3
37	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Goat weed	Asteraceae	6
38	<i>Canna indica</i>	Canna lily	Cannaceae	2
39	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i>	Khallei weed	Amaranthaceae	2
40	<i>Costus afer</i>	Bush cane	Costaceae	4
41	<i>Indigofera hinsituta</i>	Indigo	Fabaceae	5
42	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Goat's button	Asteraceae	2
43	<i>Stachyterpbeta cayennensis</i>	Blue rat tail	Asteraceae	2
44	<i>Aspilia Africana</i>	Haemohage plant	Asteraceae	7
	Total			693

Table 3. Percentage of Herbaceous Cover in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

Plots	Frequency	Herbaceous cover (%)
1	50	7.22
2	51	7.36
3	48	6.9
4	59	8.5
5	52	7.50
6	46	6.64
7	39	5.63
8	47	6.73
9	44	6.35
10	39	5.63
11	42	6.06

12	53	7.65
13	40	5.77
14	38	5.48
15	45	6.49
Total	693	100

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2021

Tree/Shrubs Species Composition

The vegetation composition of Ukpom Abak River Catchment, only one tree/shrub species (*Bambusa vulgaris*) was found in quadrat one with rare ecological status (Table.4). However, in quadrat 2, a total of 3 tree/shrub species were identified. They were *Bambusa vulgaris*, *Elaeis guineensis* and *Anthocleista vogelii* and all of them were rare in their ecological status. Quadrat 3 had no tree/shrubs species because the quadrat fell within the bare area of the river bank. Quadrat 4 had 2 tree/shrub species *Gmelina arborea* and *Ceiba bombax*). Tree/shrub species were not identified and enumerated in quadrat 5 due to its difficult terrain. *Funtumia africana* and *Glyphaea brevis* were found in quadrat 6 while quadrat 7 had only one species of *Bambusa vulgaris* with species of *Psidium guajava*, *Rahia Africana Ottedon* and *Ficus Spp* all being rare in their respective ecological status in quadrat 8.

Quadrat 9 had only *Bambusa vulgaris* while quadrat 10 recorded none. In quadrat, 11 *Nermbudia leavis* and *Bambusa Vulgaris* were found with only tree species of *Elaies guineensis* in quadrat 12. In quadrat 13 the same species of *Elaies guineensis* and

Table 4. General Tree/Shrub Species Composition

S/N	Quadrats	Scientific names	Common names	Family	FRQ	Ecological Status			
						A	C	O	R
1	Quadrat 1	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	Bambuseae	1				X
	Quadrat 2								
1		<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bamboo	Bambuseae	1				X
2		<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Palm tree	Asteraceae	1				X
3		<i>Anthocleista vogeli</i>	Cabbage tree	Gentianaceae	1				X
	Quadrat 3	Bare land							
	Quadrat 4								
1		<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Gmelina	Lamiaceae	1				X
2		<i>Ceiba bombax</i>	Silk cotton tree	Malvaceae	1				X
	Quadrat 5	Bare land							
	Quadrat 6								
1		<i>Funtumia Africana</i>	Rubber tree	Apocynaceae	1				X
2		<i>Glyphaea brevis</i>	Chewing stick	Tiliaceae	1				X
	Quadrat 7								
1		<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	bambuseae	1				X
	Quadrat 8								
1		<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Guava	Myraceae	1				X
2		<i>Raphia Africa otedoh</i>	Raphia palm	Arecaceae	1				X
3		<i>Ficus spp</i>	Sand paper tree	Moraceae	1				X
	Quadrat 9								
1		<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	bambuseae	1				X
	Quadrat 10	Bare land							
	Quadrat 11								
1		<i>Nermbudia leavis</i>	Boundary tree	Bimoniaceae	1				X
2		<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	bambuseae	2			X	

	Quadrat 12								
1		<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Palm tree	Arecaecea	1				X
	Quadrat 13								
1		<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Palm tree	Arecaecea	2			x	
2		<i>Musanga cecrepiodes</i>	Umbrella tree	Articaceae	1				X
	Quadrat 14								
1		<i>Neviobudia leavis</i>	Boundary tree	Bimoniaceae	2			x	
2		<i>Funtumia Africana</i>	Rubber tree	Apocynaceae	1				X
3		<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i>	African star apple	Sapotaceae	1				X
	Quadrat 15								
		<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Bamboo tree	bambuseae	1				X
				TOTAL	25				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R)

Table 5. Shrub Density in Ukpom Abak Drainage Basin Catchment

Plots	Shrub density
1	1
2	3
3	0
4	2
5	0
6	2
7	1
8	3
9	1
10	0
11	3
12	1
13	3
14	4
15	1
Total	25

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2021

Musanga cecrepiodes were also identified as the only tree/shrub species in the quadrat. Quadrat 14 had a total of 3 tree/shrubs species of *Neviobudia leavis*, *Funtumia africana* and *Chrysophyllum albidum* while *Bambusa Vulgaris* was the only species found in quadrat 15 but all of them indicating rare in their respective ecological status. This simply means that, those enumerated plant species are extinct in the area due to the erodibility effect and human encroachment through agricultural expansion and other anthropogenic activities.

The results presented in Table 5 shows that the presence of shrubs in the river catchment. A total of 25 shrub stands were recorded. The low density of shrubs in the area may be attributed to the continuous farming activities carried out around the river catchment. This denies the land of appreciable number or stands of shrub. A visit to the river catchment showed pockets of farmlands with cassava stems. Despite their low stands in the area, their presence in the area contributes substantially to soil erosion control and soil loss. Their existence in the area helps to give cover to the soils making them resistant to rapid soil loss. The root systems and cover help to save the soils from the destructive effects of soil erosion. This goes a long way in decreasing the erodibility status of soils in the river catchment. As reported by Styczen

and Morgan (1995), tree and shrub densities reduce soil erosion by enhancing infiltration, intercepting raindrops and by providing surface roughness through the addition of organic substances to the soil. The authors further stated that the plant roots have a mechanical effect on soil strength. By penetrating the soil mass, roots reinforce the soil and increase the soil shear strength. Zuazo and Pleguezuelo (2009) also stated that roots bind soil particles at the soil surface and increase surface roughness and through this they reduce the susceptibility of the soil to erosion. This goes to show that the vegetation components in the area have hydrological effects on the soil by increasing surface roughness, soil permeability and help to increase soil infiltration capacity.

Herbaceous Cover

Herbaceous cover was observed to be dense which may be attributed to the early rains as well as the availability of moisture. The percentage herbaceous cover measured in the river catchment is shown in Table 2. The high herbaceous cover in the area may be attributed to the exposure to solar radiation and absence of dense canopy cover usually provided by trees. This was also observed by Buba (2015) to influence herbaceous density under canopy cover. The high herbaceous cover around the river basin therefore implies that soils in the area are well protected from the impacts of heavy rainfall and other denudational forces that result in surface runoff and soil loss. According to Zuazo and Pleguezuelo (2009), plant cover protects soils against erosion by reducing water runoff. The authors further stated that herbaceous cover like other plant covers influences erosion mainly by intercepting rainfall and protecting the soil surface against the impact of rainfall drops and by intercepting runoff. The study carried out by Bochet *et al.* (2006) to investigate the influence of plant morphology and rainfall intensity on soil loss and runoff at the plant scale revealed that individual plants were helpful in interrill erosion control at the microscale, and the different plant morphologies and plant components explained the different erosive responses. The study found canopy cover to play a key in reducing runoff and soil loss, and that the litter cover beneath of plants was fundamental for erosion control during intense rainfall (Bochet *et al.*, 2006).

Tree/Shrubs Species Composition

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Quadrat 9 had only *Bambusa vulgaris* while quadrat 10 recorded none. In quadrat, 11 *Nermbudia leavis* and *Bambusa Vulgaris* were found with only tree species of *Elaies guineensis* in quadrat 12. In quadrat 13 the same species of *Elaies guineensis* and *Musanga cecrepiodes* were also identified as the only tree/shrub species in the quadrat. Quadrat 14 had a total of 3 tree/shrubs species of *Nermbudia leavis*, *Funtumia africana* and *Chrysophyllum albidum* while *Bambusa Vulgaris* was the only species found in quadrat 15 but all of them indicating rare in their respective ecological status. This simply means that, those enumerated plant species are extinct and the area due to the erodibility effect and human encroachment through agricultural expansion and other anthropogenic activities.

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area helps to give cover to the soils making them resistant to rapid soil loss. The root systems and cover help to save the soils from the destructive effects of soil erosion. This goes a long way in decreasing the erodibility status of soils in the river catchment. As reported by Styczen and Morgan (1995), tree and shrub densities reduce soil erosion by enhancing infiltration, intercepting raindrops and by providing surface roughness through the addition of organic substances to the soil. The authors further stated that the plant roots have a mechanical effect on soil strength. By penetrating the soil mass, roots reinforce the soil and increase the soil shear strength. Zuazo and Pleguezuelo (2009), also stated that roots bind soil particles at the soil surface and increase surface roughness and through this they reduce the susceptibility of the soil to erosion. This goes to show that the vegetation components in the area have hydrological effects on the soil by increasing surface roughness, soil permeability and help to increase soil infiltration capacity.

Selected physical and chemical properties of soils in Ukpom Abak River

Catchment

Physical soil properties

The physical properties of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment River are presented in Table 6. The soils are principally sandy; with sand accounting for more than 90 % of the inorganic mineral fragment in the soil. The high sand content observed in the soil is expected as the study area is a part of the coastal plain sand of southern Nigeria, which is characterized by very sandy soils over wide expanses of land (Mark *et al.*, 2024; Essien *et al.*, 2023; Essien *et al.*, 2022). The levels of silt and clay in the soils were low. The results in Table 6 therefore show that soils in the the study area are texturally similar, being loamy sand and having been derived from the same parent material (coastal plain sand) under the same climate and topography. The bulk densities of the soils ranged from 1.24 to 1.68 g/cm³ with the mean of 1.45 g/cm³.

The bulk density values recorded for the soils were within the normal range of 1.20 – 1.60 g/cm³ recommended for agricultural soils (Acquaah, 2005) and therefore suggested that the soils might not be highly eroded. This could be due to the massive vegetation cover, presence of organic matter in the soils, low degree of water erosion and absence of compaction among other factors. According to Brady and Weil (2007).

Table 6. Physical Properties of Soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

Soil	Soil depth (cm)	Particle size distribution			TC	BD (g/cm ³)	PD (g/cm ³)	Porosity (%)	Moisture (%)	WAS (%)	K x 10 ⁻⁴ (cm/Sec)
		Clay	Silt	Sand							
L1	0-15cm	10.0	7.0	88.0	LS	1.52	2.42	37.0	17.09	35.10	42.5
L2	0-15cm	6.0	8.0	85.0	LS	1.56	2.18	28.0	15.42	12.88	35.0
L3	0-15cm	7.0	13.0	80.0	LS	1.49	2.70	S45.0	13.97	54.94	51.2
L4	0-15cm	11.0	6.0	83.0	LS	1.67	2.52	34.0	15.07	39.64	28.4
L5	0-15cm	10.0	10.0	80.0	LS	1.53	2.35	35.0	6.66	20.10	39.5
L6	0-15cm	11.0	8.0	81.0	LS	1.46	2.62	44.0	7.02	14.13	50.5
L7	0-15cm	5.0	11.0	84.0	LS	1.38	2.60	47.0	8.69	12.75	50.2
L8	0-15cm	2.0	13.0	85.0	LS	1.25	2.60	52.0	9.79	36.0	56.4
L9	0-15cm	9.0	10.0	81.0	LS	1.34	2.52	47.0	6.70	15.76	55.2
L10	0-15cm	11.0	9.0	80.0	LS	1.26	2.66	53.0	6.60	26.64	60.0
L11	0-15cm	10.0	8.0	87.0	LS	1.54	2.41	36.0	17.08	36.9	43.4
L12	0-15cm	7.0	9.0	86.0	LS	1.57	2.17	27.0	15.43	11.89	36.0
L13	0-15cm	8.0	12.0	81.0	LS	1.48	2.71	45.0	13.98	55.93	50.3
L14	0-15cm	10.0	7.0	84.0	LS	1.68	2.53	35.0	15.08	39.65	29.5
L15	0-15cm	9.0	9.0	80.0	LS	1.54	2.34	34.0	6.68	21.09	38.6

L16	0-15cm	11.0	10.0	82.0	LS	1.45	2.61	43.0	7.03	15.14	51.5
L17	0-15cm	6.0	12.0	83.0	LS	1.39	2.61	48.0	8.68	13.75	50.3
L18	0-15cm	2.0	9.0	84.0	LS	1.26	2.60	53.0	9.79	37.0	57.5
L19	0-15cm	8.0	10.0	80.0	LS	1.24	2.53	48.0	6.71	14.77	55.3
L20	0-15cm	10.0	8.0	81.0	LS	1.33	2.67	54.0	6.62	27.65	61.0
Mean		8.15	9.45	82.75		1.45	2.52	42.25	10.70	27.09	47.12

Source: Researcher's fieldwork analysis (2021)

Key: L = Soil location, TC = Textural class, LS = Loamy sand, BD = Bulk density, PD = Particle density, WAS = Water aggregate stability, K = Hydraulic conductivity

Soil bulk density is affected primarily by texture and structure as well as organic matter content, such levels of soil bulk densities help improve air/water movement and root penetration. Singer and Munns (2002) reported that soils with high bulk densities inhibit water movement and root penetration; while Imoro *et al.* (2012) reported that as soil becomes more and more compacted, bulk density increases, meaning soil bulk density is an indicator of soil compaction. High bulk density is an indicator of low soil porosity and soil compaction, and it impacts available water capacity, root growth, and movement of air and water through soil. Therefore, the low bulk densities in the present study suggest low compaction and high soil porosity which can have negatively effect on soil erodibility.

The particle densities of the soils were in the range of 2.17 – 2.71 g/cm³ with the mean value of 2.52 g/cm³. Particle density data are used to better understand the physical and chemical properties of the soil. These values fall within the common range of 2.55 to 2.70 g/cm³ among agricultural soils and this could mostly be due to low compaction.

The result of soil porosity shown in Table 6 revealed that the mean value of porosity in the River Basin was 42.25%. This means that porosity levels of the studied soil is fairly high. The possible reason for this may be attributed to the presence of herbs, shrubs and few tree stands which help to loosen the soil layer. The presence of vegetation components in the area help to improve the soil physical properties. The results obtained are consistent with the finding of Offiong and Iwara (2012) and Aweto (2013) that fallow soils are observed to improve the physical properties of the soil. This is because, bulk density and porosity exhibits inverse association, as increase in one result in the decrease of the other and vice versa (Forth, 2006).

The mean content of soil moisture in the River Basin was 10.70 percent (Table 6). The high moisture content in the studied soil is low and this may be attributed to the decrease in shrub and tree density that could not afford the soil layer adequate cover from loss of water to evaporation and evapotranspiration. In a related study, Aweto (1981) stated that increase in soil moisture may be attributed to increased organic inputs. Similarly, Aweto (2013) stated that the increase in soil water-holding capacity depends primarily on organic matter acceleration. The low soil moisture in the River Basin could be attributed to the decrease in vegetation component as a result of the intensive and continuous farming activities carried out in the area.

The mean content of water aggregate stability of soil in the River Basin was 27.09 percent. This value means that soil of the River Basin has high aggregate stability. This is further influenced by the content of soil organic matter. According to USDA (1996), soils that have a high content of organic matter have greater aggregate stability. The study stated that additions of organic matter in the soil increases aggregate stability. Aggregation influences erosion, movement of water, and plant root growth. Desirable aggregates are stable against rainfall and water movement (USDA, 1996). The value of aggregate stability of the studied soil could be said to be facilitating movement of water in the soil as well as encouraging plant root growth. The result of hydraulic conductivity of the River Basin is presented in Table 6. The

mean content was 47.12 cm/sec. This means that the hydraulic conductivity of the soil is high. Soil hydraulic conductivity is the ability of a soil to transmit water. The high hydraulic conductivity in the soil may be attributed to the high soil porosity which makes it easier for water to infiltrate into the soil.

Selected chemical properties of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

The selected chemical properties of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment are presented in Table 7. Soil pH values in the study area varied from 5.4 to 6.6 with the mean value of 5.7, indicating that most of the soils were moderately acidic (pH 5.5 – 6.0) and these were consistent with the findings of Agbede (2008) that the pH of the soils in southern Nigeria is within the range of 4.5 – 6.5. The moderately acidic condition of soils in the river catchment could be attributed to reduction in leaching and erosion due to the existence of vegetal cover especially herbaceous cover that affords the soil appreciable amount of protection.

The contents of organic matter (OM) in the soils (Table 7) ranged from 0.34 – 2.58% with the mean value of 1.36%, indicating low to moderate contents (FPDD, 1990). The moderate contents of organic matter in the studied soils was attributed to the high plant density and cover in the area. The vegetal cover in the area appeared to contribute litter/dead leaves to the soils which enhanced the organic matter contents of most of the soils, apart from protecting the soils from excessive organic matter losses through water erosion and other physical soil degradation processes. Soil organic matter content could be affected by factors such as land use, and land use change is

Table 7. Selected Chemical Properties of Soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

Soil	Soil depth (cm)	pH	OM(%)
L1	0-20cm	5.6	0.34
L2	0-20cm	5.7	1.37
L3	0-20cm	5.5	1.55
L4	0-20cm	5.7	1.20
L5	0-20cm	5.9	1.03
L6	0-20cm	5.8	1.37
L7	0-20cm	5.8	1.89
L8	0-20cm	6.0	2.06
L9	0-20cm	5.7	1.20
L10	0-20cm	5.7	1.72
L11	0-20cm	5.7	0.86
L12	0-20cm	5.6	1.20
L13	0-20cm	5.4	1.03
L14	0-20cm	5.8	1.87
L15	0-20cm	5.8	0.86
L16	0-20cm	5.7	0.86
L17	0-20cm	6.0	1.37
L18	0-20cm	5.6	1.03
L19	0-20cm	5.8	2.58
L20	0-20cm	5.7	1.89
Mean		5.7	1.36

Source: Researcher’s fieldwork analysis (2021)

Key: L = Soil location, O/M = Organic matter often directly related to organic matter changes. When organic matter increases, soil aggregate stability usually improves; consequently, more stable soil structure develops and promotes faster water movement thereby resisting erosion (Brady and Weil, 2007).

Erodibility status (K-factor) of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

Erodibility status (K-factor) of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment results shown in Table 8, shows that the K-factor values of soils in the study area ranged from 0.0309 to 0.0713 $\text{thahha}^{-1}\text{MJ}^{-1}\text{mm}^{-1}$ with the mean value of 0.0533 $\text{thahha}^{-1}\text{MJ}^{-1}\text{mm}^{-1}$ indicated low status and the permeably well-drained conditions of the soils. Similar K-factor values were reported by earlier researchers (Abu *et al.*, 2016; Ibaje, 2016). According to Olson (1984) cited by Emeka-Chris (2014) and Okorafor *et al.* (2018), soils with K-factor values of 0.0 - 0.1 are regarded as permeable outwash well drained soils with permeable sub-strata.

The results (Table 8) show that soils across the sampled locations of the river catchment had similar K-factor of < 0.1. The the low eodibility status of the soils may be attributed to the dense vegetation cover around the river catchment. In a related study, Abua *et al.* (2016) reported low K-factor values for some soils in Etekwo River Basin in Akwa Ibom State and attributed the low values to high and dense vegetal cover in the river basin. According to the researchers, the high and dense vegetal cover in the river basin must have promoted high permeability because of the pore spaces created by roots of the plants in the soils. The availability of spore spaces and the presence of organic matter whose built-up is encouraged by high vegetal cover in soils help loosen the soils and allow water to seep through the soils rapidly.

Table 8. Erodibility (K-factor) Status of Soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment

Soil	VFS (%)	M	2.1M ^{1.14}	SG (S)	PC (P)	K-factor ($\text{thahha}^{-1}\text{MJ}^{-1}\text{mm}^{-1}$)
L1	6.20	1188.00	6722.18	3	5	0.0521
L2	6.50	1363.00	7862.21	3	5	0.0483
L3	6.21	1786.53	5096.73	3	5	0.0699
L4	6.72	1132.08	6362.67	3	5	0.0469
L5	5.22	1369.80	7906.94	3	5	0.0564
L6	6.13	1257.57	7172.75	3	5	0.0509
L7	7.12	1721.40	10259.46	3	5	0.0653
L8	6.30	1891.40	11422.27	3	5	0.0705
L9	6.24	1478.75	8627.79	3	5	0.0598
L10	6.16	1349.24	7771.79	3	5	0.0529
L11	5.72	1234.80	3345.19	3	5	0.0309
L12	5.64	1361.52	7852.48	3	5	0.0554
L13	7.10	1757.20	10503.05	3	5	0.0713
L14	6.26	1193.40	6757.02	3	5	0.0486
L15	6.33	1395.03	8073.18	3	5	0.0582
L16	5.78	1404.42	8135.16	3	5	0.0476
L17	6.25	1715.50	10219.38	3	5	0.0679
L18	5.67	1437.66	8355.02	3	5	0.0590
L19	7.11	1574.12	9264.94	3	5	0.0567
L20	6.32	1288.80	5081.58	3	5	0.0378
Mean	6.25	1515.23	7839.59	3	5	0.0553

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2021

Key: L = Soil location, VFS = Percentage of very fine sand, M = Product of (%Silt + %VFS) and (100 - %Clay), SG = Structure grade, PC = Permeability class, K = Soil Erodibility.

Matter content in the Etekwo drainage basin soil since organic matter are derived from decayed leaves and twigs (Abua *et al.*, 2016). The finding further suggests that soils around Ukpom Abak River Basin are

permeable outwash well drained soils with permeable sub-strata. This finding is a knowledge base for soil conservation and management practices within the study area. The low K-factor further implies that soils Ukpom Abak River Basin are less erodible. This is because Emeka-Chris (2014) reported low K-factor and stated that low K index means the soil has a high cohesion and a good interlocking force which could resist weathering forces (detachment and transportation by water).

Relationships between soil properties and K-factor

This part of the analysis gives answer to the fourth research objective which is to examine the nature of relationship between K-factor, organic matter, sand, silt, clay, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, bulk density, particle density and soil moisture. It also gives answer to the first research hypothesis that the relationships between K-factor, organic matter, sand, silt, clay, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, bulk density, particle density and soil moisture in Ukpom Abak River Catchment are not significant. The results obtained are shown in Table 9. The Pearson's correlation showed a positive and significant correlation between organic matter and K-factor ($r = 0.942$, $p < 0.05$). This result is consistent with those of Ibaje (2016) and Bonilla and Johnson (2012) who reported a positive association between organic matter and K-factor. The positive association implies that increase in organic matter in the soil would result in a corresponding increase in K-factor. This suggests that the erodibility status of the soil is enhanced with the increase in the contents of organic matter. This is expected as presence of organic

Table 9. Pearson Correlations between Soil Properties and K-factor

Variables	K-factor		Multiple R (MCA)
	r-values	Sig.	
OM (%)	0.942*	0.000	0.996*
Sand (%)	0.081	0.758	
Silt (%)	0.158	0.507	
Clay (%)	-0.246	0.296	
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	-0.308	0.187	
Particle density (g/cm ³)	0.336	0.147	
Porosity (%)	0.361	0.118	
Moisture (%)	-0.258	0.272	
Water aggregate stability (%)	0.005	0.982	
Hydraulic conductivity (cm/sec)	0.207	0.380	

Key: OM = Organic matter, *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Matter in the soil helps to loosen and increase the pore spaces which make it easier for rainwater to permeate or infiltrate the soil thereby reducing soil erosion and subsequent soil loss. This helps to reduce soil susceptibility to erosion. In line with this, Gyamfi *et al.* (2016) stated that soils with low organic matter content are highly susceptibility to erosion. Also, positive insignificant association was observed between sand and K-factor ($r = 0.081$, $p > 0.05$), silt and K-factor ($r = 0.158$, $p > 0.05$), particle density and K-factor ($r = 0.336$, $p > 0.05$), porosity and K-factor ($r = 0.361$, $p > 0.05$), water aggregate stability and K-factor ($r = 0.005$, $p > 0.05$) and between hydraulic conductivity and K-factor ($r = 0.207$, $p > 0.05$). The positive correlation suggest increase in the K-factor of soil around and within Ukpom Abak River Basin with the increase in the amount of sand and silt. This is expected as increase in sand makes the soil fragile and encourage soil erosion that later paves way for gullies, while increase in silt content like organic matter loosens the soil and make it easily permeable (increases rate of infiltration).

In a related study, Ibaje (2016) reported a positive association between sand content and K-factor. In a related study carried out in Central Chile by Bonilla and Johnson (2012), soil erodibility was observed to

increase with silt content ($r = 0.607$), and organic matter content ($r = 0.086$). The researchers observed that soils that contained predominantly silt are estimated to be vulnerable to water erosion. In addition, the result in Table 4.11 showed a negative and insignificant association between clay content and K-factor ($r = -0.246$, $p > 0.05$), bulk density and K-factor ($r = -0.308$, $p > 0.05$) and between soil moisture and K-factor ($r = -0.258$, $p > 0.05$). The positive correlation implies decrease in K-factor with the increase in clay content. This indeed is to be expected as soils with high clay contents are not easily erodible. This result agrees with those of Ibaje (2016) and Gyamfi *et al.* (2016) that found a negative association between clay and K-factor. This makes the soil not to be vulnerable to soil erosion and soil loss. In a related study, Diop *et al.* (2011) stated that silts and certain clay textured soils are more susceptible to erosion than other textured soil types. The study further reveals that bulk density is inversely related to soil erodibility. Similar result was reported by Wang *et al.* (2016).

The negative association suggests that increase in bulk density brings about a substantial decrease in K-factor. This is expected as the bulk density of soil in Ukpom Abak River Catchment is low compaction with soil porosity which negatively impact on soil erodibility. This is seen in the low erodibility status of the soil. Since the soil is not compacted, it allows rainwater to infiltrate into the soil which reduces the rate of soil loss via erosion. The negative association also means that the low bulk density of soil in the river catchment improves water movement thereby minimizing soil loss. Furthermore, result of multiple correlation analysis (MCA) indicated that the relationship between K-factor, organic matter, sand, silt, clay, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, bulk density, particle density and soil moisture in Ukpom Abak River Catchment is significant ($r = 0.996$, $p < 0.05$). This gives answer to the first research hypothesis. The result obtained in this study is consistent with the finding of Gyamfi *et al.* (2016).

In addition, the associations between K-factor and soil properties are further shown in Figures 2 – 6. The association between sand content and K-factor revealed an increasing trend (Figure. 2), which implied that K-factor increased with the increase in sand content. This result affirms that of Pearson’s correlation and depicts the relationship between the two variables as positive. The R^2 result shows that sand contents of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment are responsible for about 0.6% of

Figure 2. Sand-Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

The changes in K-factor, while about 99.4% of the unexplained variances in K-factor were attributed to other parameters not necessarily sand contents. This goes to show that sand is not the only and principal factor that influences K-factor in the study area. A look at the information and pattern portrayed in

Figure 2, reveals that most of the K-factors concentrate around sand content greater than 96%. This shows that increase in sand content above 96% brings about a corresponding increase in K-factor with the highest K-factor observed with sand content of 97%. This implies that the sand content in the study area does not help in reducing soil erodibility as the K-factor tends to increase with the increase in sand content.

The association between silt content and K-factor showed a direct association (Figure 3), as the amount of K-factor increased with an increase in silt content. The R^2 result indicates that about 2.5% changes in K-factor is caused by silt content in the soil; and that 97.5% of the unexplained variances in K-factor are attributed to other factors not necessarily silt. A look at the Figure 3, also reveals that most of the K-factors concentrate around silt content < 4%. This shows that silt content of 3% brings about a corresponding increase in K-factor with the highest K-factor observed with silt content of 2%. In all, the pattern displayed on Figure 3, is a positive association indicating the role of silt content in soil management and erosion control.

Furthermore, the pattern of association between clay content and K-factor indicated an indirect association (Figure 4). The K-factor decreases with the increase in clay content. The R^2 result indicates that clay content in the soil of Ukpom Abak River Catchment is accountable for 6% decrease in K-factor, while 94% of the unexplained variance in K-factor is attributed to other factors. Figure 4, shows that most of the K-factors concentrate around clay content of 2%. This shows that increase in clay content brings about a corresponding decrease in K-factor with the highest K-factor.

Figure 3. Silt – Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

Figure 4. Clay – Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

Factor observed with clay content of 1%. This goes to show that increase in the amount of clay in the soil will not favour K-factor as the soil will not easily absorb water or water will not infiltrate the soil thereby increasing soil erosion. In all, the pattern displayed in Figure 4 is a negative association indicating the role of clay content in soil erosion management. It goes to show soil erodibility is decreased with the increase in clay content.

The association between bulk density and K-factor showed an indirect relationship (Figure 5). This means that the level of K-factor decreases with the increase in bulk density. The R^2 result indicates that 9.4% deduction in K-factor is caused by the level of bulk density in the soil. The pattern shown in Figure 5, further reveals that most of the K-factors concentrate around bulk density content of $< 1.4 \text{ g/cm}^3$. At this level of bulk density, a greater amount of rainwater is well controlled which makes the soil unsusceptible to soil erosion. It also shows that increase in bulk density values above 1.4 g/cm^3 result in the deduction in K-factors. The decrease in soil erosion due to low soil compaction results in the decrease in the value of soil erodibility. The pattern displayed on Figure 4 therefore portrays a negative association indicating the role of bulk density in soil management and erosion control.

Lastly, the association between organic matter content and K-factor revealed an increasing trend (Figure 6), which implied that K-factor increased with the increase in the content of organic matter in Ukpom Abak River Catchment. This result reaffirms that of Pearson's correlation and portrays the nature of relationship between the two variables as positive. The R^2 result indicates that organic matter content in Ukpom Abak River Catchment is responsible for 88.7% of changes in K-factor, while

Figure 5. Bulk Density – Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

Figure 6. Organic Matter – Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

Relationship/Association between vegetation components and K-factor

This part of the analysis also gives answer to the fourth research objective which is to assess the association between densities of vegetatin components and K-factor. It also gives answer to the second research hypothesis that there are significant associations between density of herbs, density of shrub, herbaceous cover and soil erodibility. The results of the Pearson product moment correlations used to assess the associatios are shown in Table 10. It is seen fom the results that the densities of herbs ($r = -0.401$, $p > 0.05$) and herbaceous cover ($r = -0.011$, $p > 0.05$) are inversely (negatively) related to soil erodibility. The association implies that an increase in the density of herbs/herbaceous cover in the study area would result in a corresponding decrease in K-factor. This suggests that the erodibilitystatus of the soil is enhanced and made less susceptible to erosion with the increase in the density of herbs and herbaceous cover. This was anticipated because density of herbs and herbaceous cover helps to provide.

Table 10. Pearson Correlation between Vegetation Components and K-factor

Variables	K-factor		Multiple R (MCA)
	r-values	Sig.	
Density of herbs	-0.401	0.138	0.434*
Density of shrub	0.241	0.386	
Herbaceous cover (%)	-0.011	0.968	

Note: *Correlation is insignificant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Protective cover to the soil and prevent accelerated soil erosion. Their combined effects might have reduced the susceptibility of the soils to erosion. This is consistent with the findings of Zuazo and Pleguezuelo (2009) that vegetation components provide hydrological effects on the soil by increasing soil permeability and soil infiltration capacity. This goes to show that density of herbs and herbaceous cover play considerable roles in maintaining the erodibility status of soil in the River Basin.

In addition, positive association was observed between density of shrub and soil erodibility ($r = 0.241$, $p > 0.05$). The positive correlation signs suggest increase in the K-factor of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment with the increase in shrub density. A similar result was reported by Iwara *et al.* (2017) where an increase in soil erosion and nutrient loss on the 5-year old fallow was attributed to the decrease in herbaceous cover and density of shrub. The scarcity distribution of shrubs in the River Basin may be responsible for its poor protection from rainfall impact and this exposes the soil and makes it susceptible to soil erosion. Moreover, the results of multiple correlation analysis (MCA) indicated that the relationship between the density of herbs/shrubs/herbaceous cover and K-factor was insignificant ($r = 0.434$, $p > 0.05$) with density of herbs and herbaceous cover to a large extent contributing to the reduction in soil erodibility status of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment.

Additionally, the association between K-factor and vegetation components is further presented in Figure 7-9. The association between density of herbs and K-factor revealed a decreasing trend (Figure 7), which implied that K-factordecreased with the increase in the density of herbs. This result affirms that of Pearson's correla-

Correlation and depicts the nature of relationship between the two variables as negative. The R^2 result indicates that density of herbsin Ukpom Abak River Catchment is responsible for 16.1% decrease in K-factor. A look at the pattern in Figure4d revealed that decrease in K-factors was observed when density of herb is greater than 40 stems. This shows that increase in the density of herbs above 40 stands or stems brings about a corresponding decrease in K-factor. The information therefore shows that increase in the density or number of herbs in Ukpom Abak River Catchment will drastically reduce the erodibility status of soil in the area.

Figure 7. Density of Herbs-Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

The association between percentage herbaceous cover and K-factor also showed an indirect or inverse association (Figure 8), as the amount of K-factor decreased with the increase in herbaceous cover. Result in Figure 8, also reveals that most of the K-factors concentrate around herbaceous cover < 60 %. This shows that herbaceous cover greater than 60 % brings about a corresponding decrease in K-factor with the highest K-factor observed with herbaceous cover of 72.8 %. The pattern in Figure 7 shows a negative association indicating the role of herbaceous cover in soil management and erosion control.

Also, the pattern of association between shrub density and K-factor showed a direct association (Figure 9). The K-factor increases with the increase in shrub density. The R^2 result indicates that shrub density in Ukpom Abak River Catchment is accountable for 5.8% increase in K-factor, while 94.2% of the unexplained variance in K-factor is attributed to other factors. Figure 9 shows that most of the K-factors concentrate around shrub density of less than 2 stands. This shows that increase in shrub density brings about a corresponding increase in K-factor. This goes to show that increase in shrub density favours K-factor as the soil is not well protected from the impacts of heavy rainfall. In all, the pattern displayed in Figure 8 was a positive

Figure 8. Herbaceous Cover – Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

Figure 9. Shrub Density – Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Relationship

Influence of vegetation components and soil properties on K-factor

This part of the analysis gives answer to the fifth research objective which is to determine the influence of vegetation components (density of herbs, density of shrub and herbaceous cover) and soil properties (sand, silt, clay, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, bulk density, particle density, soil moisture, pH and organic matter) on soil erodibility status. It also gives answer to the second research hypothesis that organic matter, sand, silt, clay, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, bulk density, particle density, soil moisture, density of herbs, density of shrub and herbaceous cover exert significant influence on soil erodibility of Ukpom Abak River Catchment. This was achieved using stepwise multiple regression analysis. The results are presented in Table 11.

The results provide measures of understanding the importance of surface cover in controlling soil erosion and its associated losses thereby making the river catchment susceptible to erosional losses. The study reveals that soil erosion occurs in the river catchment even with the presence of vegetation components resulting in the loss of nutrient-rich topsoil. However, the presence of vegetation plays a substantial role in reducing the rate of soil erodibility in the river catchment. This is apparent as the dense herbaceous cover in the area significantly reduces runoff, sediment and nutrient loss. This indeed is indicative of the importance of vegetation in promoting hydrological functioning in the River Basin. Farmers making use of the land around the River Basin should try as much as possible to maintain adequate ground cover. The maintenance of a continuous herbaceous cover and encouraging tree density could help to deal with problems of ecological imbalance caused by forest removal for food crop cultivation. A continuous ground cover may be achieved through minimum tillage, reduced weeding and zero tillage. These practices can influence the increase in tree density and herbaceous cover which is an effective way to reduce soil erodibility.

Around the river catchment, herbaceous species like *Chromolaena odorata* (siam weed) that regenerates naturally and quickly should be allowed to grow on farmland as well as planted on fallow with scanty undergrowth or ground cover potentials to provide cover. For instance, alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) and numerous other cover crops have been planted to reduce erosional losses (Iwara *et al.*, 2017).

Among the fourteen predictor variables simultaneously entered into the model, only three were retained and significantly predicted K-factor in the study area. The results showed there was a very strong multiple correlation (0.995) between organic matter, silt, shrub density and K-factor. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) indicated that 99% of the changes in K-factor of soils in Ukpom Abak River Basin was accounted for by the combination of organic matter, silt and shrub density. This goes to show that the erodibility status of soils in the river catchment is influenced by organic matter, silt and shrub density.

The results further showed that organic matter ($t = 29.83, p < 0.05$), silt ($t = 12.08, p < 0.05$) and shrub density ($t = 2.24, p < 0.05$) exerted significant influence on the K-factor of Ukpom Abak River Catchment. This was expected considering the environmental condition of the area. Ukpom Abak River Basin is covered with vegetation components which positively favors the build-up of organic matter and silt in the soil. The presence of vegetation and the contents of organic matter and silt make soils in the river catchment unsusceptible to erosion challenges as shown by the low values of K-factor. This result implies that the extent of K-factor in the study area is principally influenced and controlled by the amount of organic matter, silt and shrub density. This is apparent because these parameters significantly impacted on soil erodibility in the river catchment. When any of these factors is in abundance, a significant percentage of K-factor is increased and this has effects on soil management. The signs of the regression coefficients showed that organic matter, silt and shrub density were positively related to K-factor. The positive sign indicates increase in K-factor with the increase in organic matter, silt and shrub density. However, the strength of each factor is ranked using the values of standardized regression coefficients (β). From the result, organic matter tends to exert more influence on K-factor than silt content and shrub density. The result shows a unit increase in organic matter holding silt content and shrub density constant will bring about 93.5% increase in K-factor, and a unit increase in silt content holding organic matter and shrub density constant will result in 37.3% increase in K-factor, while shrub density only contributes 7% being the lowest.

Table 11. Stepwise Multiple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Organic Matter, Silt and Shrub Density on the K-factor of Ukpom Abak River Basin

Predictor Variables	Coefficients		
	B	β	t-value
Organic matter content	0.000	0.935	29.829*
Silt content	4.924E-5	0.373	12.083*
Shrub density	1.077E-5	0.070	2.237*
<i>Test results</i>			
F- value	348.659*		
R	0.995		
R ²	0.990		
Constant	0.010		

Note: *Significant at 5% significance level

It shows therefore that the organic matter and silt as already noted above contributes substantially to K-factor, but organic matter is observed to be the principal soil property that determines the K-factor in Ukpom Abak River Basin. This result is expected considering the vegetation cover (shrub, herbaceous and tree cover) around and within Ukpom Abak River Basin. This condition favors the buildup of organic matter in the soil through litter droppings and decay. In a related study, FAO (2005) stated that soil organic matter content is a function of organic matter inputs (residues and roots) and litter decomposition. The increase in the amount of organic matter in the soil of the River Basin improves the soil structure (increases the pore spaces of the soil) thereby improving infiltration capacity. The increase in infiltration capacity reduces soil erosion and preserves soil quality around the River Basin which is portrayed in the low K-factor.

It is also worthy of note that organic matter causes soil to clump and form soil aggregates, which improves soil structure. With better soil structure, permeability (infiltration of water through the soil) improves, in turn improving the soil's ability to take up and hold water. The result obtained and the assertions made are consistent with those of Funderbur (2021) that organic matter serves as a pool of nutrients and water

in the soil, supports in reducing surface crusting, compaction and increases water infiltration into the soil. The study further stated that data used in the universal soil loss equation reveal that increasing soil organic matter from 1 to 3% is able to reduce erosion 20 to 33% because of increased water infiltration and stable soil aggregate formation caused by organic matter.

Also, FAO (2005) stated that when the soil is protected with vegetation and mulch, more water infiltrates into the soil rather than running off the surface. This causes streams to be fed more by subsurface flow rather than by surface runoff. The study also stated that increased soil cover can result in reduced soil erosion rates. In another study, Edehand Katan (2016) stated that organic manure decreases the bulk density of soils which helps in easing root penetration and encourages downward movement of water through old root channels. This goes to show the potential role organic matter in the soil play in improving soil structure which has positive impact on K-factor.

Summary

The present study empirically determined the erodibility status of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment. In particular, the study identified and quantified the vegetation components (herbs, trees and shrubs), determined selected physical and chemical properties of the soils and the erodibility status (K-factor) of the soils and assessed the relationships/associations between the vegetation components/soil properties and K-factor as well as the influence of vegetation components/soil properties (density of herbs, density of shrub and herbaceous cover) on K-factor. *Poaceae* was the most dominant family, while *Liliaceae* was the least plant family identified and quantified. Twenty composite soil samples were collected with a soil auger at 0 – 15 cm depth, ten each from the two sites of the river catchment, and analyzed using standard methods for particle size distribution (sand, silt and clay), porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, bulk density, particle density, soil moisture, pH and organic matter content. Soil erodibility was estimated indirectly by the Wischmeier and Smith (1978) model/equation fed with data on selected properties of soils in the river catchment. Data obtained were analysed using average, correlations and stepwise multiple regressions at 5% significance level. The findings revealed that, soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment are generally sandy with sand accounting for more than 90% of the inorganic mineral fragments and were moderately acidic with low to moderate organic matter contents. The bulk densities of the soils are low indicating low compaction and presence of organic matter in the soils.

The erodibility status of the soils were low indicating that the soils are permeable and well drained. The low K-factor obtained was attributed to the vegetation cover around the river catchment and the density of herbs and herbaceous cover were inversely related to the K-factor of the River Basin, while density of shrub is positively related to K-factor. Positive significant correlation exists between organic matter and K-factor; positive and insignificant associations exist between sand, silt, particle density, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, water aggregate stability, particle density and K-factor, while negative and insignificant associations exist between clay content, bulk density, porosity and K-factor. About 99.0% of the changes in K-factor in the soils were accounted for by the combination of organic matter, silt and shrub density.

Organic matter, silt and shrub density are observed to exert significant influence on the K-factor with organic matter being the principal soil property that determines the K-factor in the river catchment.

Conclusion

It was therefore concluded that the erodibility status of soils in Ukpom Abak River Catchment was low implying that soils in the river catchment are highly permeable and well drained.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are outlined. The vegetation around and within the Ukpom Abak River Catchment should be protected and maintained and any form of illegal logging activities and deforestation should be discouraged. Also more trees and cover crops should be planted and Governments legislations should be introduced and enforced to protect the River Catchment environment. Indiscriminate bush burning around the river catchment should be discouraged and strict punishment meted out to defaulters. Moreso, illegal sand mining should be discouraged in and around the river catchment.

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Appendix I. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 1

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	<i>Siam weed</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	6	X			
2	<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	<i>Carpet grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	2			x	
3	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	<i>Sensitive plant</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	4	x			
4	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	<i>Spiny amaranth</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	3		X		
5	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	<i>Guinea grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	4	X			
6	<i>Urena lobata</i>	<i>Caditto</i>	<i>Malvaceae</i>	3		X		
7	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	<i>Elephant grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	4	x			
8	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	<i>Red spidering</i>	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>	1				X
9	<i>Larpacea aesthes</i>	<i>Stringing herb</i>	<i>Peperaceae</i>	1				X
10	<i>Peperomia pellucid</i>	<i>Silver plant</i>	<i>Urticaceae</i>	2			x	
11	<i>Spermacole ocymoides</i>	<i>Ezema plant</i>	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	4	X			
12	<i>Saccharum octocinannum</i>	<i>Sugar cane</i>	<i>Andropogonem</i>	3		X		
13	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	<i>Bull grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	3		X		
14	<i>Larpacea ovalifolia</i>	<i>Stringing nettle</i>	<i>Urticaceae</i>	3				X
15	<i>Sida acuta</i>	<i>Broom weed</i>	<i>Malvaceae</i>	2			x	
16	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	<i>Giant blue stem grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	1				X
17	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	<i>Love grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	4	x			
			<i>Total</i>	50				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R)

Appendix II. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 2

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	<i>Calapo</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	7	X			
2	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	<i>Egg woman</i>	<i>euphorbiaceae</i>	6	X			
3	<i>Zea mays</i>	<i>Maize</i>	<i>Maydeae</i>	4	x			
4	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	<i>Devils cocoyam</i>	<i>Araceae</i>	1				x
5	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	<i>Spurge weed</i>	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	3		x		
6	<i>Spigelia entbelmia</i>	<i>Warm weed</i>	<i>Potaliaceae</i>	3		x		
7	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i>	<i>Blue cento</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	4	X			
8	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	<i>Sensitive plant</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	3		x		
9	<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	<i>Carpet grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	1				x
10	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	<i>Siam weed</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	6	X			
11	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	<i>Spiny amaranth</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	5	X			
12	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	<i>Guinea grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	4	X			
13	<i>Urena lobata</i>	<i>Caditto</i>	<i>Malvaceae</i>	1				x
14	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	<i>Elephant grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	3		x		
15	<i>Sida acuta</i>	<i>Broom weed</i>	<i>Malvaceae</i>	1				X
			<i>Total</i>	51				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix III. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 3

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	4	X		X	
2	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	5	X			
3	<i>Commelina begbalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	7	X			
4	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	4	X			
5	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	3		x		
6	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	3		x		
7	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	4	X			
8	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	2			X	
9	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	4	X			
10	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			X	
11	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	4	X			
12	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	2			X	
13	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	4	X			
			Total	48				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Appendix IV. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 4

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	3	X			
2	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	3		x		
3	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	1		x		
4	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	1				x
5	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2	X			
6	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	3		x		
7	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	3		x		
8	<i>Commelina begbalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	2			x	
9	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	3	X			
10	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	1		x		
11	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	2			x	
12	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	1				x
13	<i>Elensine indica</i>	Bull grass	Poaceae	2		x		
14	<i>Larpatar ovalifolia</i>	Striging nettle	Urticaceae	1				x
15	<i>Drymorina cordata</i>		Caryophylliaceae	2			x	
16	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	9	x			
17	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	2			x	
18	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	2		x		
			Total	44				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix V. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 5

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Red spidering	Nyctaginaceae	2			x	
2	<i>Larbatea aesthes</i>	Stringing herb	Peperaceae	1				x
3	<i>Peperomia pellucid</i>	Silver plant	Urticaceae	2			x	
4	<i>Spermacole ocymoides</i>	Ezecma plant	Rubiaceae	6	X			
5	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	8	X			
6	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	5	X			
7	<i>Spigelia enthelmia</i>	Warm weed	Potaliaceae	3		x		
8	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i>	Blue cento	Fabaceae	2			X	
9	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Sensitive plant	Fabaceae	3		x		
10	<i>Axomopus compresus</i>	Carpet grass	Poaceae	1				x
11	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	3		x		
12	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			X	
13	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	4	X			
14	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	2			X	
15	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2			X	
16	<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i>	Consumption weed	Corpparidaceae	3		X		
17	<i>Croton lobutus</i>		Euphorbiaceae	1				x
18	<i>Echinochloa pyranidalis</i>		Poaceae	1				x
19	<i>Paspalum arbiculane</i>	Ditch mullet	Poaceae	1				x
			Total	52				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R). **Source:** Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix VI. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 6

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	1		X		
2	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	2			X	
3	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	2			X	
4	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	3	X			
5	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	2	X			
6	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	1				x
7	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	3		X		
8	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	2	X			
9	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			X	
10	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	2	X			
11	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	1				x
12	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2	x			
13	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	1				x
14	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	2			X	
15	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	1			X	
16	<i>Elensine indica</i>	Bull grass	Poaceae	1			X	
17	<i>Larpater ovalifolia</i>	Stringing nettle	Urticaceae	1				x
			Total	32				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix VII. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 7

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	13	x			
2	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	1				x
3	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	2			x	
4	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	3		X		
5	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	2			x	
6	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	3		X		
7	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	1				x
8	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	4	X			
9	<i>Urena lobata</i>	Caditto	Malhaceae	1				x
10	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	3			x	
11	<i>Cyperus spp</i>		Cyperaceae	1				x
12	<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i>	Consumption weed	Corpparidaceae	1				X
13	<i>Croton lobutus</i>		Euphorbiaceae	4	x			
			Total	39				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix VIII. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 8

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Spigelia enthelmia</i>	Warm weed	Potaliaceae	3		X		
2	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i>	Blue cento	Fabaceae	3	X			
3	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Sensitive plant	Fabaceae	4	X			
4	<i>Axomopus compresus</i>	Carpet grass	Poaceae	1				X
5	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	2		X		
6	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			X	
7	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	3		X		
8	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	3		X		
9	<i>Titbonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	1			X	
10	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	4	X			
11	<i>Commelina begbalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	2	X			
12	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malhaceae	3	X			
13	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	3		X		
14	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	2		X		
15	<i>Gloriosa superb</i>	Lily	Liliaceae	1				x
16	<i>Spermacole venticillata</i>		Rubiaceae	1			X	
			Total	36				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix IX. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 9

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	2			X	
2	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	7	X			
3	<i>Commelina begbalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	3		X		
4	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	4	X			
5	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	3		X		
6	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	2			x	
7	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	3		X		
8	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	1				x
9	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	2			x	
10	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	3		X		
11	<i>Axomopus compresus</i>	Carpet grass	Poaceae	1				x
12	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	4	X			
13	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			x	
14	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	3		X		
15	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	2			x	
16	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2			x	
			Total	44				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix X. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 10

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	22	x			
2	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	1				x
3	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	2			x	
4	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	3		X		
5	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	Euphorbiaceae	3		X		
6	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	2			x	
7	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	1				x
8	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	2			x	
9	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	3		X		
			Total	39				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XI. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 11

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	9	X			
2	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			x	
3	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	4	X			
4	<i>Urena lobata</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	3		X		
5	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	4	x			
6	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	1				x
7	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	1				x
8	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	5	x			
9	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	6	X			
10	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	4	X			
11	<i>Kyllingobulbosa</i>	Sedge	Cyperaceae	3		x		
			Total	42				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XII. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 12

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	5	X			
2	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			x	
3	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	6	X			
4	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	2			x	
5	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	8	X			
6	<i>Urena lobata</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	2			x	
7	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2			x	
8	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Beni seed	Pedaliaceae	1				x
9	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Goat weed	Asteraceae	3		x		
10	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Red spidering	Nyctaginaceae	1				x
11	<i>Larpacea aesthes</i>	Stringing herb	Peperaceae	1				x
12	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	1				x
13	<i>Caladium bicolin</i>	Devils cocoyam	Araceae	2			X	
14	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	3		x		
15	<i>Canna indica</i>	Canna lily	Cannaceae	2			X	
16	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i>	Khallei weed	Amaranthaceae	2			x	
17	<i>Costus afer</i>	Bush cane	Costaceae	5	X			
18	<i>Indigofera hinsituta</i>	Indigo	Fabaceae	3		x		
			Total	53				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XII. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 13

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Bull grass	Poaceae	3		x		
2	<i>Laripater ovalifolia</i>	Strigging nettle	Urticaceae	2		x		
3	<i>Costus afer</i>	Bush cane	Costaceae	4	X			
4	<i>Indigofera hinsituta</i>	Indigo	Fabaceae	2			x	
5	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	1	x			
6	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	6	X			
7	<i>Commelina begbalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	2		x		
8	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	3		x		
9	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	3		x		
10	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	2			X	
11	<i>Spigelia enthelmia</i>	Warm weed	Potaliaceae	2			X	
12	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i>	Blue cento	Fabaceae	1			X	
13	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Sensitive plant	Fabaceae	1		X		
			Total	33				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XIV. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 14

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	2			X	
2	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	4	X			
3	<i>Commelina begbalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	3		X		
3	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	5	X			
4	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	4	x			
5	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	4	x			
6	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	3		X		
7	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	Spiny amaranth	Amaranthaceae	2			X	
8	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	4	X			
9	<i>Urena labota</i>	Caditto	Malvaceae	2			X	
10	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	3		x		
11	<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i>	Consumption weed	Corpparidaceae	2			X	
			Total	38				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R)

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XV. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 15

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	<i>Siam weed</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	3	X			
2	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i>	<i>Spiny amaranth</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	2			X	
3	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	<i>Guinea grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	1	X			
4	<i>Urena lobata</i>	<i>Caditto</i>	<i>Malvaceae</i>	1			X	
5	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	<i>Elephant grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	3	x			
6	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	<i>Bull grass</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	3		x		
7	<i>Larpatel ovalifolia</i>	<i>Stringing nettle</i>	<i>Urticaceae</i>	1				x
8	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	<i>Beni seed</i>	<i>Pedaliaceae</i>	1				x
9	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	<i>Goat weed</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	3		x		
10	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	<i>Red spidering</i>	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>	2			X	
11	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	<i>Goat's button</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	2			X	
12	<i>Stachytarpheta cayennensis</i>	<i>Blue rat tail</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	1				x
13	<i>Paspalum ariculane</i>	<i>Ditch mullet</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	8	X			
14	<i>Aspilia Africana</i>	<i>Haemohage plant</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	2	X			
			Total	33				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XVI. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 16

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	<i>Siam weed</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	5	X			
2	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	<i>Beni seed</i>	<i>Pedaliaceae</i>	1				x
3	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	<i>Goat weed</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	1		x		
4	<i>Paspalum ariculane</i>	<i>Ditch mullet</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	1	X			
5	<i>Aspilia Africana</i>	<i>Haemohage plant</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	4	X			
			Total	12				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XVII. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 17

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Larpatel ovalifolia</i>	<i>Stringing nettle</i>	<i>Urticaceae</i>	1		x		
2	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	<i>Mexican sunflower</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	2	x			
3	<i>Commelina beghalensis</i>	<i>Wandering jew</i>	<i>Commelinaceae</i>	1		x		
4	<i>Centrosema pubescens</i>	<i>Blue cento</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	1			X	
5	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	<i>Sensitive plant</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	2		X		
			Total	7				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XVIII. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 18

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Spigelia enthelmia</i>	Warm weed	Potaliaceae	1		X		
5	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	1		X		
9	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	Asteraceae	1			X	
10	<i>Imperata cylindrical</i>	Spear grass	Poaceae	3	X			
11	<i>Commelina beghalensis</i>	Wandering jew	Commelinaceae	2	X			
12	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	1	X			
14	<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	Love grass	Poaceae	1		X		
16	<i>Spermacole venticillata</i>		Rubiaceae	1			X	
			Total	11				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XIX. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 19

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	1		X		
2	<i>Calapogonium mucunoides</i>	Calapo	Poaceae	3	X			
3	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Egg woman	euphorbiaceae	2	X			
4	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	2	X			
5	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	2	X			
6	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2	x			
7	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	1			X	
8	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Bull grass	Poaceae	1			X	
			Total	14				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XX. Herbaceous species composition in quadrat 20

S/N	SCIENTIFIC NAMES	COMMON NAMES	FAMILY	FRQ	Ecological Status			
					A	C	O	R
1	<i>Chromoleana odorata</i>	Siam weed	Asteraceae	1	X			
2	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass	Poaceae	1		x		
3	<i>Brachiaria deflex</i>	Elephant grass	Poaceae	2	X			
4	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Broom weed	Malvaceae	3	X			
5	<i>Andropogon tectorum</i>	Giant blue stem grass	Poaceae	2		x		
6	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Bull grass	Poaceae	1		x		
7	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Maydeae	4	x			
8	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Spurge weed	Euphorbiaceae	1		x		
			Total	15				

Note: species frequency of 4 and above is Abundant (A), 3 Common(C), 2 Occasional (O) and 1 Rare (R).

Source: Authors field analysis 2021

Appendix XXI. Stepwise multiple regression result

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	OM	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter ≤ .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove ≥ .100).
2	Silt	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter ≤ .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove ≥ .100).
3	Shrub density	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter ≤ .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove ≥ .100).

a. Dependent Variable: Erodibility status

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.919 ^a	.845	.833	.0000812
2	.992 ^b	.985	.982	.0000264
3	.995 ^c	.990	.987	.0000229

a. Predictors: (Constant), OM
b. Predictors: (Constant), OM, Silt
c. Predictors: (Constant), OM, Silt, Shrub density

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.000	1	.000	71.020	.000 ^b
	Residual	.000	13	.000		
	Total	.000	14			
2	Regression	.000	2	.000	390.220	.000 ^c
	Residual	.000	12	.000		
	Total	.000	14			
3	Regression	.000	3	.000	348.659	.000 ^d
	Residual	.000	11	.000		
	Total	.000	14			

a. Dependent Variable: Erodibility status
b. Predictors: (Constant), OM
c. Predictors: (Constant), OM, Silt
d. Predictors: (Constant), OM, Silt, Shrub density

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.010	.000		159.420	.000
	OM	.000	.000	.919	8.427	.000
2	(Constant)	.010	.000		409.952	.000
	OM	.000	.000	.948	26.609	.000
	Silt	4.948E-5	.000	.375	10.517	.000
3	(Constant)	.010	.000		462.519	.000
	OM	.000	.000	.935	29.829	.000
	Silt	4.924E-5	.000	.373	12.083	.000
	Shrub density	1.077E-5	.000	.070	2.237	.047

a. Dependent Variable: Erodibility status

Excluded Variables ^a						
Model		Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
		Tolerance				
1	Sand	-.374 ^b	-7.309	.000	-.904	.903
	Silt	.375 ^b	10.517	.000	.950	.994
	Clay	.314 ^b	3.528	.004	.714	.801
	Shrub density	.080 ^b	.707	.493	.200	.968
	Herbaceous cover	.225 ^b	2.306	.040	.554	.941
	Density of herbs	-.098 ^b	-.835	.420	-.234	.883
	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	.191 ^b	1.730	.109	.447	.849
	Particle density (g/cm ³)	.043 ^b	.350	.733	.100	.834
	Porosity (%)	-.078 ^b	-.615	.550	-.175	.776
	Moisture (%)	.085 ^b	.733	.478	.207	.921
	Water aggregate stability (%)	.192 ^b	1.942	.076	.489	.999
	Hydraulic conductivity (cm/sec)	-.133 ^b	-1.187	.258	-.324	.920
pH	.055 ^b	.444	.665	.127	.840	
2	Sand	-.105 ^c	-1.241	.241	-.350	.169
	Clay	.065 ^c	1.241	.241	.350	.447
	Shrub density	.070 ^c	2.237	.047	.559	.968
	Herbaceous cover	.036 ^c	.842	.418	.246	.693
	Density of herbs	-.040 ^c	-1.058	.313	-.304	.863
	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	.012 ^c	.263	.798	.079	.679
	Particle density (g/cm ³)	.000 ^c	-.007	.994	-.002	.824
	Porosity (%)	-.007 ^c	-.172	.866	-.052	.754
	Moisture (%)	.030 ^c	.776	.454	.228	.902
	Water aggregate stability (%)	.060 ^c	1.667	.124	.449	.856
	Hydraulic conductivity (cm/sec)	-.011 ^c	-.271	.791	-.081	.828
	pH	-.002 ^c	-.056	.957	-.017	.824
3	Sand	-.087 ^d	-1.178	.266	-.349	.167
	Clay	.054 ^d	1.178	.266	.349	.441
	Herbaceous cover	.003 ^d	.072	.944	.023	.577
	Density of herbs	-.030 ^d	-.885	.397	-.270	.844
	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	-.032 ^d	-.742	.475	-.228	.545
	Particle density (g/cm ³)	.008 ^d	.224	.827	.071	.814
	Porosity (%)	.019 ^d	.495	.631	.155	.681
	Moisture (%)	-.014 ^d	-.356	.729	-.112	.633
	Water aggregate stability (%)	.043 ^d	1.290	.226	.378	.797
	Hydraulic conductivity (cm/sec)	.024 ^d	.628	.544	.195	.690
	pH	-.004 ^d	-.120	.907	-.038	.823
	a. Dependent Variable: Erodibility status					
b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), OM						
c. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), OM, Silt						
d. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), OM, Silt, Shrub density						

Appendix XXII. Correlation (vegetation components)

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Soil erodibility	.010855	.0002089	20
Shrub density	1.67	1.291	15
Herbaceous cover	68.573	7.2578	15
Density of herbs	46.20	6.085	15

Correlations					
		Soil erodibility	Shrub density	Herbaceous cover	Density of herbs
Soil erodibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.241	-.011	-.401
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.386	.968	.138
	N	20	15	15	15
Shrub density	Pearson Correlation	.241	1	.305	-.200
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.386		.270	.475
	N	15	15	15	15
Herbaceous cover	Pearson Correlation	-.011	.305	1	.188
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.968	.270		.501
	N	15	15	15	15
Density of herbs	Pearson Correlation	-.401	-.200	.188	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.138	.475	.501	
	N	15	15	15	15

